

Synthesis in the 4-Azafluorene Group. Part III

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The pyridine synthesis developed by Krohnke et al¹ have now been extended to the synthesis of 4-azafluorene and 4-azafluorenone. The limitations of the synthesis have been studied and alternative routs to the 4-azafluorene ring system have been explored. The fragmentation pattern of the mass spectrum of the 4-azafluorene (XIV) has been interpreted. A synthesis of 1-benzylideneindan-2-one is also described.

KROHNKE and coworkers¹ developed a novel synthesis of pyridines based on Michael addition of suitable pyridinium salts such as (VI-VIII) to α, β -unsaturated ketones using ammonium acetate as the source of nitrogen. When applied to benzylideneindan-1-one (IX) an elegant synthesis of 1,3-diphenyl-4-azafluorene resulted. Since azafluorenones are known to be physiologically active², the experiments described in the present communication were carried out employing arylideneindan-1,3-diones (I-V)^{2,3} with the ultimate end of studying the scope and limitations of the above synthesis.

- (I) R=C₆H₅
- (II) R=C₆H₄Me (p)
- (III) R=C₆H₄(OMe)(o)
- (IV) R=C₆H₄NO₂ (m)
- (V) R=C₆H₄NO₂ (p)
- (VI) PhCOCH₂PyBr
- (VII) CH₂COCH₂PyBr
- (VIII) CNCH₂PyCl

- (IX) R=C₆H₅
- (X) R=C₆H₄NO₂ (o)
- (XI) R=C₆H₄NO₂ (m)

When arylideneindan-1,3-diones were treated with phenacylpyridinium bromide(VI) and ammonium acetate, the reaction took a different course giving the pentacyclic pyridines (XII) and surprisingly, the same result was obtained by using acetonilpyridinium bromide(VII) or cyanomethylpyridinium chloride (VIII). It was clear that a different reaction was taking place in preference and this could be traced to the dissociation and recombination of (I) to (XIII, R=O) and thence to (XII, R=Ph). This assumption was supported by the following facts: (i) Benzylideneindan-1,3-dione (I) alone gave (XII, R=Ph) with ammonium acetate, (ii) benzylideneindan-1-one (IX) gave (XIV, R=Ph) with ammonium acetate and (iii) bis-benzylideneindan-1-one (XIII, R=2H) also gave (XIV, R=Ph) with ammonium acetate in good yield. Oxidation of (XIV, R=Ph) with chromic acid gave (XII, R=Ph) and Wolff-Kishner reduction of (XII, R=Ph) gave (XIV, R=Ph). The azafluorene (XIV) showed molecular ion peak at m/e 331 (C₂₅H₁₇N) followed by salient fragmentation ion peaks at m/e 254, m/e 253, m/e 241, m/e 165, m/e 164 and m/e 88. The formation of these ions may be rationalised according to the following scheme:

Our experiments however were more fruitful when we employed a modified Hantzsch⁴ synthesis on (I) with β -phenyl- β -aminoacrylonitrile in acetic acid. The product (XVI), was aromatised (chromic acid) to (XVII), then hydrolysed to the acid (XVIII) and decarboxylated to the desired azafluorenone (XIX). The intermediate (XVII) could also be obtained by W-K reduction of (XVI) to (XXII) followed by chromic acid treatment. The azafluorene

m/e 241 (M=90):

m/e 164 (m/e 241-77):

renone (XIX) on W-K reduction afforded the 1, 3-diphenyl-4-azafluorenone (XXIV).

The cyanohydropyridine (XXII) was isolated in small quantity by a further adaptation of the foregoing Hantzsch* synthesis on benzylideneindan-1-one (IX) with (XV). Here again the main product was (XIV, R=Ph) (the aminonitrile was the obvious source of ammonia needed in its formation).

Benzylideneindan-1-one (IX) on treatment with acetonilpyridinium bromide (VII) and ammonium acetate gave 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-azafluorene (XXI) along with (XIV, R=Ph). The structure of the former was established by its synthesis from the ester (XX) by hydrolysis, decarboxylation and

W-K reduction. This reduction was extended to *o*-methoxybenzylideneindan-1-one in a similar manner.

Reaction of arylideneindan-1-one with cyanomethylpyridinium chloride gave 1-aryl-3-amino-azafluorenes (XXIII).

1-Benzylideneindan-2-one (XXVI), hitherto unknown, and some 2-arylideneindan-1-ones have been reported by Harman *et al.*^{4a}; may be expected to give 1-azafluorene by an extension of the work adumbrated above. The compound has now been isolated from the known ester (XXV)⁵ by hydrolysis and decarboxylation. Although preliminary experiments with pyridinium salts have not been encouraging, further experiments are underway to prepare 1-azafluorene and its derivatives.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The infra-red spectra were recorded in Perkin Elmer Infracord Model 237 Spectrophotometer.

Benzylideneindan-1-one (IX) :

A mixture of indan-1-one (0.7 g) and benzaldehyde (0.5 g) was dissolved in ethanol (8 ml) and conc. hydrochloric acid (5 drops) was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed on water bath for four hours, and the product, m. p. 110-11° (yield, 0.5 g) was identical with that prepared according to Mills and Akers⁶ using zinc chloride as catalyst. (Found : C, 86.80 ; H, 5.75. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{12}O$: C, 87.24 ; H, 5.49%). The other substituted benzylideneindan-1-ones were also prepared in the similar manner. *p*-Nitrobenzylideneindan-1-one (X) as yellow needles, m. p. 250-51°. (Found : C, 72.34 ; H, 5.21. $C_{16}H_{11}NO_2$ requires C, 72.44 ; H, 4.18%) ; *m*-nitrobenzylideneindan-1-one (XI) as light yellow needles, m. p. 194-96°. (Found : C, 72.41 ; H, 4.94. $C_{16}H_{11}NO_2$ requires C, 72.44 ; H, 4.18%).

Attempted synthesis of 1,3-Diphenyl-4-azafluorenone (XIX) :

A mixture of 2-benzylideneindan-1,3-dione (0.2 g), phenacylpyridinium bromide (VI, 0.225 g), ammonium acetate (0.62 g) and glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was allowed to reflux for two hours. The reaction mixture was then slowly cooled to room temperature when yellow crystals that separated were filtered and washed with water. The filtrate and the washings on further dilution gave a second crop of crystals. The product 2,3,5,6-dibenzoylene-4-phenylpyridine was crystallised from pyridine

methanol in yellow needles, m. p. 355-56° (yield, 90 mg) ; $\nu_{C=O}$ 1720 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 83.54 ; H, 3.69. $C_{26}H_{18}NO_2$ requires C, 83.56 ; H, 3.62%).

The dioxime was obtained as needles, m. p. 301-02°. (Found : C, 77.10 ; H, 4.12 ; N, 10.75. $C_{25}H_{15}N_2O_2$ requires C, 77.11 ; H, 3.88 ; N, 10.79%). Similarly prepared 2,3,5,6-dibenzoylene-4-(2'-methoxyphenyl)pyridine (XII) was obtained as yellow needles, m. p. 320-21° ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1710 cm^{-1}). (Found : C, 80.18 ; H, 3.91. $C_{26}H_{15}NO_2$ requires C, 80.20 ; H, 3.86%) ; 2,3,5,6-dibenzoylene-4-(3'-nitrophenyl)pyridine as yellow needles, m. p. 365° ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1710 cm^{-1}), (Found : C, 74.25 ; H, 3.35. $C_{25}H_{13}N_2O_4$ requires C, 74.25 ; H, 2.97%) ; 2,3,5,6-dibenzoylene-4-(4'-nitrophenyl)pyridine as yellow needles, m. p. 360° ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1712 cm^{-1}), (Found : C, 74.23 ; H, 3.25. $C_{25}H_{12}N_2O_4$ requires C, 74.25 ; H, 2.97%) ; 2,3,5,6-dibenzoylene-4-(4'-methylphenyl)pyridine as yellow needles, m. p. 360-61° ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1710 cm^{-1}), (Found : C, 83.53 ; H, 4.04. $C_{26}H_{15}NO_2$ requires C, 83.63 ; H, 4.05%).

2,3,5,6-Dibenzoylene-4-phenylpyridine (XIV, R=Ph) :

A mixture of 2-benzylideneindan-1-one (IX ; 0.55 g), phenacylpyridinium bromide (0.7 g), ammonium acetate (2.0 g) and glacial acetic acid (3 ml) was allowed to reflux for two and half hours. The crystals of 2,3,5,6-dibenzoylene-4-phenylpyridine was filtered and crystallised from pyridine-methanol in colourless needles, m. p. 292-93° (Found : C, 90.57 ; H, 5.53. $C_{26}H_{17}N$ requires C, 90.60 ; H, 5.17%). Picrate, yellow needles, m. p. 265-66° (Found : C, 67.13 ; H, 2.55 ; N, 9.88. $C_{81}H_{14}N_4O_7$ requires C, 67.14 ; H, 2.52 ; N, 10.10%).

2,3,5,6-Dibenzoylene-4-phenylpyridine (XII) :

2,3,5,6-Dibenzoylene-4-phenylpyridine (0.1 g) in glacial acetic acid (4 ml) was treated with chromic acid (0.1 g) in a little water. The chromate of the base separated as an orange precipitate. The mixture was heated on water bath till the solution turned completely green (*ca.* 5 hours). The compound crystallised from pyridine-methanol in yellow needles, m. p. 356-57° ($\nu_{C=O}$, 1720 cm^{-1}), (Found : C, 83.55 ; H, 3.68. $C_{25}H_{18}NO_2$ requires C, 83.56 ; H, 3.62%).

The above compound (XII, 0.1 g) and hydrazine hydrate (100%, 4-5 drops) in ethylene glycol (5 ml) was heated on oil bath at 200° for 2-3 hours. On cooling (XIV, R=Ph) was obtained, m. p. 292-93° (yield, 0.06 g). (Found : C, 90.59 ; H, 5.20. $C_{26}H_{17}N$ requires C, 90.60 ; H, 5.17%).

1,3-Diphenyl-4-azafluorenone-2-carboxylic Acid (XVIII) :

A mixture of 2-cyano-1,3-diphenyl-4-azafluorenone (0.4 g) and hydrochloric acid (3 ml) was heated in a sealed tube at 160-70° for two hours. 1,3-Diphenyl-4-azafluorenone-2-carboxylic acid separated from pyridine as brownish yellow needles, m. p.

212-14° (yield, 0.25 g) ($\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ 1708 cm^{-1} , ν_{COOH} 1737 cm^{-1}). (Found : C, 79.48 ; H, 4.01. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_3$ requires C, 79.56 ; H, 40.01%).

1, 3-Diphenyl-4-azafluorenone (XIX) :

The foregoing acid (0.1 g) was heated carefully with Cu-bronze on a metal bath at 310-20° giving 1-3-diphenyl-4-azafluorenone which crystallised from pyridine-methanol in yellow needles, m. p. 169-70° (yield, 0.05 g) identical with an authentic specimen¹.

2-Cyano-1, 3-diphenyl-1, 4-dihydro-4-azafluorene (XXII) :

A mixture of 2-cyano-1, 3-diphenyl-1, 4-dihydro-4-azafluorenone (XVI), 0.2 g, hydrazine hydrate (100%, 2-3 drops) in ethylene glycol (3 ml) was heated in oil bath at 200° for two and half hours. The reaction mixture was then cooled and diluted with water. 2-Cyano-1, 3-diphenyl-1, 4-dihydro-4-azafluorene was collected, crystallised from benzene in dirty cream-coloured needles, m.p. 215-16°. (Found : C, 86.66 ; H, 5.42. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2$ requires C, 86.67 ; H, 5.24%).

2-Cyano-1, 3-diphenyl-4-azafluorenone (XVII) :

A solution of chromic acid (0.1 g) in a little water was added to a solution of 2-cyano-1, 3-diphenyl-1, 4-dihydro-4-azafluorene (0.1 g) in glacial acetic acid (4 ml). On working up 2-cyano-1, 3-diphenyl-4-azafluorenone crystallised from pyridine-methanol in cream-coloured needles, m. p. 274-75° ($\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ 1712 cm^{-1} ; $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$, 2208 cm^{-1}). (Found : C, 83.75 ; H, 3.85 ; N, 7.70. Calc. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}$: C, 83.80 ; H, 3.91 ; N, 7.80%).

1,3-Diphenyl-4-azafluorene :

1, 3-Diphenyl-4-azafluorenone (XIX) (0.1 g) was mixed with hydrazine hydrate (100% ; 4-5 drops and ethylene glycol (3 ml) and heated in oil bath at 200° for three hours. The compound was obtained as colourless needles from pyridine-methanol, m. p. 158-59°. (Found : C, 90.25 ; H, 5.35. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}$ requires C, 90.25 ; H, 5.37%).

2-Cyano-1, 3-diphenyl-1, 4-dihydro-4-azafluorene (XXII) :

A mixture of benzylideneindan-1-one (IX, 0.2 g), β -phenyl- β -aminoacrylonitrile (XV, 0.14 g) and glacial acetic acid (2 ml) was refluxed for 4-5 hours. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and set aside for two days. The product, m.p. 294-95° was identified as 2,3,5,6-dibenzylene-4-phenyl pyridine (XIV, R=Ph). The filtrate on dilution with water gave an oily compound which partly solidified on long standing. This was filtered and titrated with benzene to give (XXII) as cream-coloured needles, m.p. 212-14°. (Found : C, 86.65 ; H, 5.40. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2$ requires C, 86.67 ; H, 5.24%).

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-azafluorenone (XXI)

A mixture of benzylideneindan-1-one (0.65 g),

acetylpyridinium bromide (VII, 0.6 g), ammonium acetate (1 g) and glacial acetic acid (4 ml) was refluxed for 3 to 4 hours and then worked up as usual. After removing (XIV, R=Ph), the filtrate was basified with sodium carbonate solution and then extracted with ether. 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-azafluorenone (XXI, R=H ; R'=Me) was isolated as an oil and its picrate crystallised from glacial acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 232-33° (decomp.). (Found : C, 61.72 ; H, 4.01 ; N, 11.51. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{O}_7$ requires C, 61.72 ; H, 3.72 ; N, 11.52%).

1-(2'-Methoxyphenyl)-3-methyl-4-azafluorenone :

A mixture of *o*-methoxybenzylideneindan-1-one (0.625 g), acetylpyridinium bromide (0.537 g), ammonium acetate (0.5 g) and glacial acetic acid (4 ml) was refluxed for 3-5 hours. The compound which separated was crystallised from pyridine-methanol in light yellow needles, m.p. 135-36°. (Found : C, 83.58 ; H, 6.21. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}$ requires C, 83.59 ; H, 5.96%).

Ethyl 1-phenyl-3-methyl-1, 4-dihydro-4-azafluorenone carboxylate (XX, R=COOEt ; R'=Me)

A solution of benzylideneindan-1, 3-dione (2.5 g) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was treated with ethyl β -amino crotonate (3 g) at boiling point. A deep red colour immediately developed, followed by separation of ethyl 1-phenyl-3-methyl-1, 4-dihydro-4-azafluorenone carboxylate (XX) which separated from acetic acid in dark red plates, m.p. 251-52°. (Found : C, 76.92 ; H, 4.95 ; $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_3$ requires C, 76.93 ; H, 4.92%).

Ethyl 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-azafluorenone-2-carboxylate :

The foregoing dihydro compound (XX, 0.2 g) was dissolved in warm acetic acid and treated with chromic acid (0.3 g) in water (2 ml). Ethyl 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-azafluorenone-2-carboxylate crystallised from alcohol in lemon plates, m.p. 173-74° ($\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ 1720 cm^{-1} ; ν_{COOEt} 1735 cm^{-1}). (Found : C, 76.93 ; H, 5.45. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_3$ requires C, 76.95 ; H, 4.99%).

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-azafluorenone-2-carboxylic Acid :

The foregoing ester (0.2 g) was refluxed with 70% sulphuric acid (4 ml) at 160-80° for three hours giving 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-azafluorenone-2-carboxylic acid which was obtained as needles from pyridine-methanol, m.p. 314-15° (decomp.). (Found : C, 76.18 ; H, 4.47. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_3$ requires C, 76.19 ; H, 4.16%).

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-azafluorenone :

A mixture of the foregoing acid (0.5 g), copper²⁺

bronze (80 mg) and quinoline (4 ml) was refluxed for six hours. The azafluorenone crystallised from methanol in light yellow needles, m.p. 123-24° ($\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ 1712 cm^{-1}). (Found : C, 84.05 ; H, 4.92. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}$ requires C, 84.11 ; H, 4.83%).

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-azafluorene (XXI, $R=H$; $R'=Me$) :

A mixture of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-azafluorenone (0.1 g) and hydrazine hydrate (100% ; 0.5 c.c.) in ethylene glycol (4 ml) was heated at 180-90° for two hours and then at 225-30° for another one hour. The product (oil) gave a picrate which crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 233-34° (decomp.). (Found : C, 61.72 ; H, 4.60 ; N, 11.43. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_7$ requires C, 61.73 ; H, 3.69 ; N, 11.55%).

1-(o-Methoxyphenyl)-3-amino-4-azafluorene (XXIII) :

A mixture of *o*-methoxybenzylideneindan-1-one (0.625 g), *N*-cyanomethylpyridinium chloride (0.40 g), ammonium acetate (1.5 g) and glacial acetic acid (4 ml) was refluxed for 3 hours. The product crystallised from pyridine in light yellow needles, m.p. 138-39°. (Found : C, 79.12 ; H, 6.01 ; $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires C, 79.14 ; H, 5.59%). Similarly, 1-(*m*-Nitrophenyl)-3-amino-4-azafluorene (XXIII) crystallised as light cream needles from pyridine, m.p., 199-201°. (Found : C, 71.25 ; H, 4.35. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$ requires C, 71.27 ; H, 4.32%).

Ethyl 3-benzylideneindan-2-one-1-carboxylate (XXV) :

It was prepared by the method of Scroth and Treibes⁵ by condensing benzaldehyde with ethyl indan-2-one-1-carboxylate in the presence of 20% ethanolic potassium hydroxide.

Benzylideneindan-2-one :

Ethyl 3-benzylideneindan-2-one-1-carboxylate (0.1 g) was mixed with sulphuric acid (20% ; 2 ml) and heated on steam bath for nearly 2 and half hours. On cooling the reaction mixture was extracted with ether and treated with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and the oily product distilled at 200°C/0.5 mm. ($\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ 1685 cm^{-1}). (Found : C, 87.24 ; H, 5.60. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}$ requires C, 87.24 ; H, 5.49%). The 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone as yellow plates, m.p. 222-23° (decomp.). (Found : 65.98 ; H, 4.22. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$ requires C, 65.99 ; H, 4.03%).

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